

Smart Farming Network

Testimonial

Alain Chotard, French farmer from Brittany, relies on the collective for equipment management. Alain owns the major part of his material in a Cuma (farmers' cooperative where producers undertake collective investments). Therefore, he does not hesitate to join other farmers for upgrading equipment for the field crops. For instance, his Cuma recently bought a fertilizer spreader with GPS.

Inventive, he also occasionally builds the material he needs by himself. Recently, together with his trainee, he made a plastic mulch collector machine, that removes plastic covers from plant beds, recycles them, thereby enabling them to be used for the next crop.

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SMART AKIS PARTNERS:

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Smart AKIS is the European Network on Smart Farming

Our goal is to enable the European farming community to treat Smart Farming Technologies as normal and so bridge the gap between practice and research by identifying and delivering new Smart Farming solutions to fit farmers' needs.

Smart AKIS is aware that many Smart Farming solutions are available in the market now, but that many social and economic obstacles still remain for the wider adoption of such technologies by farmers who increasingly demand that new solutions fit their requirements.

The Network is supported by the European Commission through the Horizon 2020 programme and the European Innovation Partnership Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability (EIP-AGRI).

Who are we targeting?

As a Thematic Network, Smart AKIS adopts a multi-actor approach, targeting all actors involved in agricultural innovation processes, such as farmers, farmer-associations, research, advisory and extension services, agronomists and agricultural consultants, agricultural equipment suppliers and providers of smart farming solutions.

Smart AKIS services and results

Research

Smart AKIS is surveying more than 270 farmers and experts all over Europe to understand and respond to the:

- Needs and interests of Smart Farming by farmers from France, Germany, Greece, Netherlands, Serbia, Spain and UK.
- Factors hindering the adoption of Smart Farming in Europe.

Innovation support

Smart AKIS is holding Innovation Workshops, including to generate innovations and to assist the marketing and uptake of projects on Smart Farming in France, Germany, Greece, Netherlands, Serbia, Spain and UK.

If you are interested on taking part in Smart AKIS Innovation Workshops, you can contact your Smart AKIS Contact Point.

France

Pauline Bodin, ACTA. pauline.bodin@acta.asso.fr

Germany

Klaus Erdle, DLO. k.erdle@dlg.org

Greece

Matina Voulgaraki, Agricultural University of Athens (AUA). stavou@aua.gr

Serbia

Milica Trajkovic, BioSense. trajkovic.milica.ns@gmail.com

Spain

Alberto Lafarga, INTIASA. alafarga@intiasa.es

The Netherlands

Harm Brinks, Delphy. h.brinks@delphy.nl

UK

David Tinker, David Tinker & Associates / EurAgEng. d.tinker@ntlworld.com

Smart Farming Platform

Smart AKIS has developed an online and free platform open to farmers, researchers, industry and advisory services with the following services:

- **Technology database.** Browse, search and assess a broad database of Smart Farming technologies available now in the market and expected soon from research projects; get useful information on how they work, their economic and environmental benefits and view demonstrations and other information material.

- **Quick assessment tool.** If you need guidance and advice on the Smart Farming Technologies most suited to your needs, you can fill in a short survey that will propose those most closely fitting your needs.

- **Technology feed.** If you are a company providing smart farming technologies or a researcher, you can feed your products and solutions into the Platform's smart farming technology database.

- **Message board.** A moderated Message Board will be open to farmers, advisory services, agronomists, researchers and companies, allowing questions on the use of a given technology, searches for partners for collaboration, dissemination of events, surveys for testing new products or the need for new smart farming technologies, etc. This will build an open community users involved with and practicing smart farming.

You can register for the Smart Farming Platform on www.smart-akis.com

smart AKIS
Smart Farming Thematic Network

